

ST04: Culture-Nature Journey, exploring the complexities of human relationships with natural and cultural places

CULTURAL LANDSCAPE OF KUTTANAD: A UNIQUE COASTAL WETLAND OF KERALA AND HOW INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE REINFORCE WETLAND PRESERVATION

Rekha V Kumar

Research Scholar, Dept. of Architecture & Regional Planning,
Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, West Bengal, India 721302,
Email: ar.rekhav@gmail.com

Dr. Sanghamitra Basu

Associate Professor , Dept. of Architecture & Regional Planning ,
Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur , West Bengal , India 721302,
Email: sbasu@arp.iitkgp.ernet.in

Abstract

Wetlands are unique settings which are not only a repository of rich natural and cultural resources but also are examples of unique human – nature interaction , enlightening the way how life of a set of people nurtures the very existence of wetlands and vice versa . Communities linked to wetlands have traditionally been depending on wetlands for their resources, and in the process engaged in services and practices which assigned further values, including spiritual values, to the unique natural settings of the wetlands. Unfortunately, in absence of a proper understanding of multi-layered aspects of cultural heritage and their interdependence with natural phenomenon, these links are now been weakened, and it can be argued that their depletion destroys both natural and cultural heritage of the wetlands. In this context, this paper studies evolution of Kuttanad in Kerala , a specific wetland region with unique geographic setting, where the dependency of the inhabitants on its resources, led to the formation of certain beliefs and customs that they still follow as a part of their lifestyle. This region of Kuttanad is a low lying region in Kerala, where wetlands are formed by combination of coastal backwaters, rivers, marshes, paddy fields and water channels. This paper explores the evolution of Kuttanad wetland region and its people, mainly to understand the traditional systems practiced by various communities in the region and how these have shaped its cultural landscape. Based on a few case studies, the paper looks at cultural practices, various beliefs and customs practiced by the people and how these customs and practices have helped to install respect of nature and maintain ecological balance of this wetland region.

Key words: wetlands, cultural landscape, heritage, ecological balance.

Introduction

Wetlands are precious, bio-diverse environment with unique natural habitat and cultural heritage properties¹. The Convention on Wetlands of International Importance (Ramsar Convention) defines wetlands as “areas of marsh, fen, peatlands, or water, whether natural or artificial, permanent or temporary, with water that is static or flowing, fresh, brackish or salt, including areas of marine waters, the depth of which at low tide does not exceed six metres”². The relationship between wetlands and people extends far beyond the value of the natural resources or the vital services of wetlands. It includes a rich cultural heritage that has evolved over time, concerned with the conservation and wise use of wetlands.

1.EAC 2000 OP1

2. Convention on Wetlands 1971

The cultural heritage takes many forms, from human-made physical structures and artefacts, palaeontological records in sediments and peats, and places of special religious significance, to traditional water and land use management practices that have sustained human populations and crafted unique wetland cultural landscapes³. Many of the traditional techniques people have evolved to manage wetlands for exploitation – whether it be to agriculture, salt extraction, make use of mangrove trees, fishing or farming have stood the test of time as techniques that both sustain people and conserve wetlands. Maintaining these techniques as well as the traditional knowledge that lies behind them, is widely recognized as a key tool in the conservation of biological diversity. Wetland destruction and the loss of traditional management practices means not only the loss of the more tangible values related to wetland such as flood control, groundwater replenishment, nutrient cycling etc but also the loss of our wetland cultural heritage.

The term cultural heritage refers to the complex whole of life's activities, including those beliefs, values, customs, mores, and traditions that are embodied in folklore and ethnography, and related to environmental concepts at the local level. Some of these cultural values are important enough to be passed on to future generations, and become part of our human heritage. This heritage can be tangible or intangible, may have different meanings for different stakeholders, and its values may change over time. It includes traditional knowledge and wisdom associated with natural resources, cultural landscapes formed from agricultural patterns, oral traditions and languages, as well as events and ceremonies either secular or spiritual. When it comes to wetlands, cultural values and heritage manifest themselves through salt harvesting, reed cutting, fishing, the weaving of nets, agricultural practices, boat building, animal grazing, hunting, and the building of huts, roofs and fish-traps with reeds. These everyday activities are deeply entwined with wetlands and are important to promote environmental management and contribute to nature conservation.

The key objective of this paper is to explore the intimate relationship between the inhabitants and the region, by focusing on the intangible cultural heritage that binds them to their landscapes. This paper is a part of an ongoing research on Cultural Landscape of Coastal Wetlands and focuses on a new approach to the issues in the region, taking into account the mind-set of the inhabitants and expected to have constructive results for future developmental activities.

Intangible Cultural Heritage

UNESCO defines : "The Intangible Cultural Heritage means the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills –as well as the instruments, objects, artefacts and cultural spaces associated therewith- that communities, groups and, in some cases, individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage. This intangible cultural heritage, transmitted from generation to generation, is constantly recreated by communities and groups in response to their environment, their interaction with nature and their history, and provides them with a sense of identity and continuity, thus promoting respect for cultural diversity and human creativity⁴."

The Intangible Cultural Heritage encompasses the following domains :

- a) Oral traditions and expressions, including language (e.g. songs, lullabies, story-telling etc)
- b) Performing arts (e.g. music, dance, traditional theatre, puppet-plays, painting, calligraphy etc)
- c) Social practices, rituals, and festive events (e.g. festivals, processions, games, weddings etc)
- d) Knowledge and practices concerning nature and universe (e.g. traditional medicine, traditional architecture, traditional navigation systems, traditional methods of utilizing clean energy, traditional management systems etc)
- e) Traditional craftsmanship (e.g. traditional knowledge and skills of pottery-making, felt-making, textile-making, wood-work, metal-work, jewelry-making, musical instrument making etc).

3. Papayannis, T (2008)

4. The 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage, Article 2

In this context, this paper studies a specific wetland region, Kuttanad in Kerala, with unique geographic setting, where the dependency of the inhabitants on its resources, led to the formation of certain beliefs and customs that they still follow as a part of their lifestyle and all these aspects have led to an interesting mosaic of Intangible Cultural Heritage worth exploring.

Case Study : Kuttanad, Kerala

Kuttanad is a delta region of about 900 sq. km situated in the west coast of Kerala (Fig 1) shaped by the confluence of four major rivers the Meenachil, the Manimala, the Pampa and the Achenkoil draining into the Vembanad Lake, a Ramsar site. Geologically Kuttanad is considered as a recent sedimentary formation. In the geological past, the entire area was a part of the Arabian Sea. Though the boundary of Kuttanad is rather loosely defined and the extent of its area has been variously computed at different times, today it encompasses 79 revenue villages, 10 Taluks and 3 Districts. The agriculture of Kuttanad wetlands is again unique because in large areas, the rice cultivation is being done up to 2 m depth below the sea level. The challenge is how to conserve this unique ecosystem along with the economic stake it involves because of its conservation. This will imply that the livelihood security of the farm, fisher and other families living in this area must be strengthened through better infrastructure and multiple avenues of market driven income earning opportunities.

The field study was conducted during two different time periods. The first visit conducted during South West Monsoon (First week of June) included personal visits to Kuttanad Taluk Office and reconnaissance survey through the periphery of Moncombu, Nedumudy and Pulikunnu villages and resulted in collecting primary data through photographs, reports, unstructured interview with inhabitants. Second field study was conducted before North East Monsoon (First week of October) collecting information through focus group surveys regarding the perception of inhabitants. Based on the field visits, this study looks into the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Kuttanad.

With the aim of identifying the cultural-natural resources in and around Kuttanad, this study mainly concentrated on one particular village, Moncombu which is surrounded by Manimala river and Venattukadu Canal. This study is an attempt to understand the inter relationship between inhabitants and the region which ended up in the significant role of intangible cultural heritage in preserving the Kuttanad wetlands. Secondary data through reports and articles provided the base for field surveys.

History and Evolution of Kuttanad⁵

There are many legends on the origin of Kuttanad. According to one legend, Kuttanad was believed to be forest with dense tree growth. This forest was destroyed subsequently by a wild fire. Chuttanad (the place of the burnt forest), was eventually called Kuttanad. It is a well known fact that burned black wooden logs were mined from paddy fields called as 'Karinilam' (Black paddy fields), from areas in and around Thottappally until the recent past. This fact throws some light on this theory of Chuttanad evolving to Kuttanad. Kuttanad is partly a natural formation in the back water caused by the deposit of silt and sand by the rivers while some parts were developed through reclamation of shallow parts of the back waters.

Evolution of Kuttanad and land reclamation :

During 8th Century AD to 1950s, reclamation of Kayal lands in Kuttanad land happened in three phases.

1st Phase : Reclamation of Vembanad Lake started in 1834 for paddy cultivation. 250 ha of land got reclaimed. Reclamation became a trend by 1870s

2nd Phase: The second phase started during 1888. In 1903, Travancore Government was forced to ban reclamation upon pressure from the Presidency Government of Madras which feared that reclamation was harming the Cochin Port due to piling up of sand at the port's mouth.

3rd Phase: The 3rd phase started during 1912 with the lifting of the ban on reclamation. Nearly 5000 ha were reclaimed during this phase. The introduction of mechanical pump set that could drain deep back waters within a shorter time became crucial for rapid change. In 1940s, part of the Vembanad Lake was reclaimed by an enterprising landlord, Muricken for paddy cultivation. By later part of 19th century and by the beginning of the 20th century, its full potential was realised when mechanized pump-sets fuelled by Kerosene or crude oil came into practice. In the aftermath of Land Reforms Act in 1950, the landlords all over Kuttanad had to divide their land among the workers on the basis of "pattam".

In 1970s the government took over all the land reclaimed by Muricken and the land distributed to the workers as a part of Land reforms act. Reclamation stopped by 1980's. The area now has 15000 ha of reclaimed land and 40,000 ha of natural land

Landscape of Kuttanad

The complex mosaic of Kuttanad can be physiographically grouped into three types :

Raised Lands : 0.5 m to 2.5m above MSL with coconut as the major crop

Water Areas : Large expanse comprising the rivers and lake system in which roughly 13000 ha are actively used for fishing and other water based livelihoods.

Wetlands: A landscape with levels ranging from 0.60m to 2.00m below MSL, part of which are reclaimed lands and form the traditional paddy cultivation areas called Puncha vayals. Puncha Vayals are with abundant sediments, sand, silts and even buried remains of huge trees and dead vegetation.

These three landscape elements have been used in a remarkable way that show how the traditional management techniques and ingenious practices of local communities made possible the cultivation of rice below the sea level and enhance the complex ecosystem services for rice, fish-shell-clam production.

Paddy Cultivation and Peoples' perspective

The paddy fields (Puncha vayals) of Kuttanad is intricately connected with the local landscapes that also link the inhabitants to the region and to a common past.

A focus group survey has been conducted to get an insight to traditional practices and peoples' perspective. During the focus group survey, through the inhabitants' memories, beliefs, and narratives, a wider contextual and thematic perspective is revealed; the narratives do not only relate to local beliefs but also portray the inhabitants' (both old and new generations') sense of place, attachments, mentalities, feelings, sentiments and emotions, their local religious beliefs, their livelihood patterns and the way their life is blend with the resources and life in the region. The condition of traditional occupations including paddy cultivation and people's attitude towards such hereditary occupations are also brought to notice by their accounts. It also throws light on the demographic composition, the manner of social grading as well as the changes in the relationship between the various social sections.

Life and Lifestyle of People

In Kuttanad, life merges with the land and the water. Agriculture being the main activity, women labourers work in the green paddy fields, with a landlord or an overseer to supervise them (Fig 2).

Boat is an indispensable part of each household, for fishing, clam collection, duck rearing (Fig 3) and transportation. Almost all houses have small boats tied in front with strong coir ropes.

The ferry men ferry people across the rivers that pay them a few rupees for each ride.

Food and Livelihood security of Kuttanad wetlands

Kuttanad is predominantly an agriculture belt of Kerala, where people are dependent on paddy cultivation and allied activities like fishing, animal husbandry, clams collection etcetera for livelihood. Agriculture is the major livelihood of people in Kuttanad. Rice and coconut are major crops cultivated in this area. Kuttanad Landscape, including the Puncta Rice System that surrounded with estuaries, flood plains, lakes, ponds and canal networks is rich with diverse fish wealth. Various species of clams are reported from the region and its harvesting for meat is still an important livelihood option for the poor families of the region. Large quantity of lime shell deposits (white clam) is a characteristic feature of the Vembanad Lake and the inner lake regions.

Rice-fish Rotation farming of Kuttanad.

Rice –fish rotation is an emerging practice of the system, as double cropping of rice turned to be less lucrative and more damaging to environment. The rotation also helps in not only getting high yield for the rice, but less disease and pest problems for the crop.

Tools and craftsmanship related to livelihoods

Living and working in a wetland environment has produced an amazingly diverse heritage of traditions and material products. Fishing even though not the primary activity in Kuttanad, it is associated with movable heritage of effectively designed local boats with an immense range of capture tools – nets and traps predominate, ranging from gill nets, seine nets and cast nets to permanently constructed traps in lakes, rivers and estuaries as well as smaller, movable traps.

Screw pine, Typha in the region offered enough raw material for mat weaving – a livelihood option for the women. Wetlands are important in coir processing and various coir products like mats, baskets, floor coverings etcetera were manufactured even centuries ago.

Traditional Land Management Practices, Construction of Polders and Land Reclamation

Some ancient traditional management practices continue to be used successfully even today. The process of reclamation would start with identification of the shallow regions in the vast stretches of Vembanad Lake and marking the boundaries by erecting bamboo poles, which are subsequently protected with construction of strong bunds around the boundaries. The bund construction (Fig 4) and maintenance are the most skillful tasks.

The Janmi – Kudiyan (Landlord – Labourer) system as cultural information resource

The Janmi- Kudiyan system had played a significant role in social and cultural development in Kuttanad. Through a long stretch of history, Pulayas (lower caste people) have been the backbone of wetland rice cultivation. Although they were integral to agrarian production, they were prevented from owning land in Kerala's traditional caste society. This means the ownership of land was concentrated in the hands of a few individual landlords.

Cycle of Monsoons

Life in Kuttanad seems to move in a cycle imposed upon them by the resources surrounding them, around which their life revolve. The rhythm of their life is determined by the resources (the land and water) that surround them. Movement and transportation becomes very difficult in times of floods as important highways in the locality get submerged under two to four feet of water. Floods have become a part of their life. The silt deposited by the floods make the region more and more fertile every year making it fit for paddy cultivation. The flood also cleans the region removing pollution in water and land and also clears the pola from the water-bodies making movement possible.

Practice of Human Sacrifice

Human sacrifices are believed, by the inhabitants of Lower Kuttanad, to have been the ultimate way to save the paddy fields when the bunds breached in times of heavy floods. Surrounded by water on all sides, cultivation was done 2 to 2.5 meters below water level and when the mud bunds encircling the fields breached, the labourers were ready to make the supreme 'sacrifice', in order to save the crop, to serve their landlord (Thampuram) and to give life. Even though real human sacrifices ceased, the people's utmost belief in 'sacrifices' seems to have instinctively remained in their minds and the practise later continued in the form of symbolic rituals, which continues even today.

Kuttanad – an inspiration in art , music , literature and folklore

Kuttanad have stimulated the creative talents of humans from the earliest times, producing a great wealth of folklore, stories, songs and the unforgettable rhythm of snake boat songs. The early dependency of most people in Kuttanad generated a rich oral tradition of songs, stories and literature transferred through generations of many centuries, that were collective expressions of wetlands and often helped to maintain traditional management practices. They are still part of everyday life for many of them. Kuta Chozhi (Fig 5) is a folk dance performed by farm labourers celebrating the rice harvesting.

Musical rhythm is central to the life of villagers in Kuttanad. The thuds of Vallapattu (boat songs) and the music of Chakrapattu (water wheels) (Fig 6) have become essential part of their daily lives.

Spiritual Life of Kuttanad

Water is essential for life, and therefore people's belief systems have, from earliest times, commonly considered water and wetlands to be sacred. Although now diminished in some cultures, this sacramental relationship between people and wetlands is still in evidence today in many parts of the the Kuttanad region, ensuring the conservation and wise use of wetlands.

Festivals and Events of Kuttanad (Table 1)

Water and wetlands have been key factors for Kuttanad in celebrating many ancient festivals. Religious festivals and regional events are associated with climate (monsoons) , fertility and good fortune. Boat races are the most significant events conducted for centuries during the regional festival of Onam. While many ancient traditions are still practised, over the centuries most people have become physically distanced from wetlands in their everyday life, yet wetlands remain a source of inspiration, sometimes in quite different ways.

Boat Races and Boats as cultural cult of Kuttanad.

The boat races (Fig 7) are unique water festival of Kuttanad. The large number of participants in a racing boat still marks the uniqueness as no other sport in the world has such a large number in a team. The synchronized way of rowing needs long and devoted training and inherent aptitude. Most of the major water festivals of the region are associated with legends connected with famous temples . These festivals best retain the flavour of ancient Kerala culture, especially the Uthirithathi boat race on the Pampa , in Aranmula, where devotion, music and the sheer artistry and grandeur of the boats, known as Palliyodams , make it a unique experience for the spectators .

Conclusion

The Conference of the Parties (COP) of the Ramsar Convention has recognized the value of the cultural heritage and traditional uses of wetlands to the conservation of such areas and the wise use of their resources. Towards that end, Article VIII of the COP encourages incorporation of relevant aspects of cultural heritage into both the design and implementation of wetland management plans. The Convention on Biological Diversity, on the other hand, recognizes the role of indigenous and local communities in conservation in situ. The Convention's preamble acknowledges the "close and traditional dependence of many indigenous and local communities embodying traditional lifestyles on biological resources, and the desirability of sharing equitably benefits arising from the use of traditional knowledge, innovations and practices relevant to the conservation of biological diversity and the sustainable use of its components"

As keepers of cultural information resources, the people of Kuttanad possess a wealth of indigenous knowledge and local experience on wetland management. With this information, they can adopt development models which emphasize economic growth but do not jeopardize socio-cultural and environmental sustainability. They should chart their own development path and balance their development strategies, making use of their cultural heritage to strengthen self-reliance in their quest for progress and development. To be more specific, the people of Kuttanad with appropriate government support, should be able to effectively link their legislative framework and traditional practices into the nexus of sustainable development and protection of the environment.

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Figures and Tables

Figure 1 – Location and Map of Kuttanad , Source : Kerala Land Use Board

Fig 2- Agricultural labourer women working under the supervision
Source
<https://www.keralatourism.org/destination/kuttanad/>

Fig3 - Duck Rearing
Source: -<http://bobkrist.com/photography/kerala-india>

Fig 4 - Traditional Bund Construction Techniques
Source: MSSRF Report

Fig 5-Kuda Chozhi Folk Harvest Dance
Source - <https://artkerala.weebly.com/chozhikali.html>

Fig 6 – Singing chakrapattu while dewatering the paddy fields
Source : <https://www.keralatourism.org/alappuzha/59/>

Fig 7 - Nehru Trophy Boat Race
Source - <http://nehrutrophy.nic.in>

Months	Weeks	Malayalam Months	Climatic Cycle and Human Activities	Festivals and Events
January	First	Dhanu		Pulinkunnu Church Perunnal
	Second			
	Third	Makaram		
	Fourth		Rice Harvesting	Kannadi Temple Festival – 3 days
February	First	Kumbham		
	Second			
	Third			
	Fourth			
March	First	Meenam		Festivals in Temples -Pulinkunnu Temple 8 days , Kavalam Temple 10 days, Nedumudy Temple 8 days
	Second			
	Third			Champakulam Church Perunnal
	Fourth			
April	First	Medam	Field Preparation	Vadayar Temple Festival – 1 day
	Second			Moncombu Temple Festival – 10days
	Third			St George Church Feast Edathua 27th April to 7th May
	Fourth			Changanassery Temple Festival – 3 days
May	First	Edavam	Sowing the seeds	
	Second			
	Third			Moolam Boat Race – Midhunam Moolam
	Fourth			
June	First	Midhunam	South West Monsoon Edavappathy	
	Second			
	Third		Chakara – Fishermen Festival	
	Fourth			
July	First	Karkidakam		
	Second			
	Third			
	Fourth			
August	First	Chingam		Nehru Trophy Boat Race – 2nd Saturday of August
	Second			Rajiv Gandhi boat race August 20th
	Third		Rice Harvesting. Kannikoythu	Kidangara boat race (Chingam - ThiruOnam)
	Fourth			Pulinkunnu Church Edavaka Perunnal from August 31st
September	First	Kanni	Dewatering and field preparation	
	Second			
	Third			
	Fourth			
October	First	Thulam	Sowing	
	Second			
	Third		North East Monsoon Thulavarsham	
	Fourth		Chakara – Fishermen Festival	Festival at Mannarasala Nagaraja Temple
November	First	Vrishchikam		Festival at Kalacode Mahadeva Temple
	Second			Festival at Sree Krishna Temple Thiruvambady
	Third			
	Fourth			
December	First	Dhanu		
	Second			
	Third			Festival at Dharamshasta temple Kalavoor
	Fourth			

Table 1 - Calendar of Festivals and Events of Kuttanad

Source : Focus Group Survey

Curriculum Vitae

Ar. Rekha V Kumar is specialised in Architectural Conservation (M-Arch) from School of Planning and Architecture New Delhi, currently pursuing PhD in the Department of Architecture & Regional Planning, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur. She is doing her research on Cultural Landscape of Coastal Wetlands. Her research interests include heritage conservation, vernacular architecture, cultural landscape and coastal environments. She is Member of Council of Architecture, India and Indian Institute of Architects.

Dr. Sanghamitra Basu is currently Associate Professor of Architecture & Regional Planning, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur. She is actively involved in teaching, consultancy, and research in the field of heritage mapping, documentation, conservation planning, and management. She has been involved with INTACH. Her research interests are in the areas of Urban Conservation, Heritage Management, Traditional Architecture, Cultural Heritage Planning, Post Modernism & Contemporary Architecture, GIS in Urban Planning. She is the Associate Member of Institute of Town Planners , India , Indian Institute of Architects; Member of Council of Architecture, India , ICOMOS, India and served as a Member of National Monuments Authority, GoI.